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Chemical Investigation of the Fruits of *Voacanga grandifolia* (Miq.) Rolfe

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OCCURRENCE of alkaloids in *Voacanga* species¹ encouraged us to chemically examine the different parts of a new *Voacanga* plant, *Voacanga grandifolia* (Miq.) Rolfe² (*Apocynaceae*). *V. grandifolia*, a native of Java, is a deciduous erect shrub. It is cultivated in the Indian Gardens. Phytochemical investigation for the first time of the fruits of *Voacanga grandifolia* has revealed the presence of three indole alkaloids and two neutral components. In the present communication we report their isolation and characterization.

Air-dried milled fruits (1 kg) were extracted with alcohol. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and fractionated into basic and non-basic constituents by churning with 5% aq. citric acid followed by filtration. The aq. citrate containing the basic components was extracted with CHCl_3 (CSC), washed with NH_4OH , dried and concentrated. The remaining aq. citrate was basified with NH_4OH , extracted with CHCl_3 (SB), washed with H_2O , dried and concentrated. Both the CSC and SB fractions were chromatographed over alumina (Brockmann activity¹) separately. The petrol (b. p. $60^\circ\text{-}80^\circ$)- C_6H_6 (1:1) eluate of the CSC fraction yielded a solid, purified as hydrochloride (15 mg), m. p. 192° , $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -370^\circ$ (MeOH). The parent alkaloid, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ (M^+ 336) was generated as an amorph. solid by basification of the hydrochloride with NH_4OH . Its uv and ir spectra indicate the presence of a β -anilinomethacrylate chromophore^{1,2} and the mass spectrum is typical of a vincadifformine-type alkaloid⁴. The identity of the alkaloid with (-) tabersonine^{5,6} was finally established by comparison with an authentic sample. Chromatography of the SB fraction afforded a solid from the C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (4:1) eluate. The solid on several crystallizations from MeOH- CHCl_3 furnished a crystalline compound (100 mg), $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ (M^+ 718), m. p. 303° (dec.) $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -311^\circ$ (CHCl_3). This was identified as vobtusine^{7,8} (uv, ir, MS, m. m. p. and Co-tlc with an authentic sample). Elution of the above chromatogram with C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (3:1) yielded the other alkaloid (40 mg), crystallized from MeOH- CHCl_3 , $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ (M^+ 352), m. p. 242° , $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +20^\circ$ (EtOH). It was finally characterized as rhazine^{9,10} by comparison (m. m. p., Co-tlc, uv, ir and MS) with an authentic sample.

The non-basic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel G. The petrol eluate gave a solid (30 mg), crystallized from MeOH, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ (M^+ 468), m. p. 214° , $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +27.2^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It was characterized as lupeol-acetate by comparison with an authentic sample

(m. m. p., superimposable ir and Co-tlc in silica gel G impregnated with AgNO_3 solution). The petrol- C_6H_6 (1:1) eluate yielded β -sitosterol, m. p. 136° ; acetate, m. p. 124° (identified by m. m. p., Co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra with an authentic sample).

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Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate

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THISTLETHWAITE has synthesized 12-Molybdophosphates of a number of metal ions by neutralization reaction between metal oxides or metal carbonates and 12-Molybdophosphoric acid.^{1,2} Following this method of synthesis 12-Molybdophosphate of Uranyl Cation has been prepared by the reaction between Uranyl Carbonate and 12-Molybdophosphoric acid.

Table—Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate

%U	%P	$\frac{UO_2}{PMo_{12}O_{40}}$	$\frac{H_2O}{PMo_{12}O_{40}}$	pH	CH ⁺	$\frac{H^+}{PMo_{12}O_{40}}$
13.78	1.291	1.39	11.5	2.19	0.006253	1.36

To an aqueous solution of 12-Molybdophosphoric acid containing a drop of concentrated nitric acid, dry Uranyl Carbonate was added in the molar ratio 1:3 respectively. The suspension was then warmed over water bath and the clear solution was filtered out from the undissolved matter. It was concentrated over water bath and the concentrated liquor was then allowed to evaporate in a dish. Shining yellow crystals of Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate appeared which were filtered washed with water and finally with alcohol. The compound was dried in sulphuric acid desiccator.

The salt is soluble in water and can be isolated from aqueous solution by crystallization. Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate is an acid salt and contains 2.78 equivalents of the UO_2^{++} cation per mole of the anion. From the elemental analysis and hydron content measurement it appears that the salt may be represented as $(UO_2)_{1.39}H_{1.36}PMo_{12}O_{40}$, 11.5 H_2O .

Analysis :

Uranium and phosphorous of the compound were determined gravimetrically as U_3O_8 and alkalimetrically via ammonium molybdate respectively.

Hydron content of the salt has been determined by taking certain weight of the substance in definite volume of water and measuring the pH of the solution. From the pH value equivalent hydrogen-ion concentration per mole of the anion $PMo_{12}O_{40}$ was calculated. Water of crystallization of the salt was determined from the weight loss of the salt after keeping at 120° - 150° for 6 hr.

Result and Discussion :

Therefore apparent basicity = $1.39 \times 2 + 1.36 = 4.13$

Considering the basicity of 12 MPA as 3, the salt can be described as 'Normal salt' with very slight deficiency of base (2.8 instead of 3). pH determinations of the salt reveals the presence of approximately one equivalent of free H^+ per mole of 12 MPA. The presence of excess hydrogen ions the salt may be explained, following Ripan³, that 12 MPA has three strong hydrogens and that further hydrogen of the hydrated salt can ionize under certain conditions. The presence of these additional H^+ seems to provide an autostabilization for the salt since, true normal salt would have neutral or alkaline pH under which circumstances the $PMo_{12}O_{40}$ anion should be degraded to similar ions. Presumably in the presence of very low concentration of added mineral acid (one drop of conc. nitric acid), more than three hydrogen ions of the hydrated complex are able to dissociate. From all the above observations it appears that the salt is an acid salt and nonstoichiometric in character in keeping with the well known base exchange properties of the 12-Molybdophosphoric acid.

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Electron Transfer Reactions. II. Oxidation of Glyoximes.

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GLYOXIMES are known to be oxidised to furoxans by potassium ferricyanide^{1,2,3}, halogens^{1,2,4}, bleaching solutions^{1,5}, oxides of nitrogen⁶, etc. While studying the coordination chemistry of the oximino ligands, we observed that halogens form addition products with some metal glyoximates⁷ and that copper sulphate oxidises phenyl hydrazone of 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide 2-oxime.⁸ Following our studies on the oxidation of phenyl hydrazone oxime by various oxidants, we carried out the oxidation of 2, 3-dioxobutyranilide dioxime (I) to the furoxan derivative (II) with various oxidants. We find that (i) oxidation with peroxydisulphuric acid or chlorine is very vigorous and gummy mass is obtained, (ii) good yield is obtained with the oxidant like lead tetra-acetate and (iii) low yield is obtained with the oxidant like potassium ferricyanide. We observe that the yield is increasing in order,

These results indicate that lead tetra-acetate and potassium permanganate can be considered more suitable for the preparation of the furoxan by the oxidation of the glyoxime. Further, two-electron oxidants bring about oxidation to a greater extent than one-electron oxidants. Recently Burakevich, Lore and Volpp⁹ have shown that syn, anti and amphi isomeric forms of phenyl glyoxime yield the same phenyl furoxan derivative, and Brokenshire, Roberts and Ingold¹⁰ have shown that both isomeric iminoxy radicals (a) $>C=N-O$ and (b) $>C=N \rightarrow O$ are obtained regardless of which of the isomeric forms is oxidised. Hence the mechanism of oxidation reaction can be represented as follows :